

CURRENT AND MODERN PROBLEMS OF CORPORATE ACCOUNTING AND REPORTING ACCORDING TO INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS.

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Annotation:

Significant differences in the conceptual principles of corporate reporting formation in different countries lead to the incompatibility of reporting, incomprehensibility of its interested users and the impossibility of making economic decisions. The globalization of financial markets requires uniform reporting standards that act as a link between issuers and investors and ensure the effective functioning of capital. There is a need for integration in the accounting field, minimizing differences in the rules for the preparation and presentation of information by national corporate reporting systems. Solving the problem of global accounting integration at the international level will provide unambiguous conclusions about the performance and financial position of corporations, comparability of corporate reporting, reduce the cost of its compilation; increase the methodological level of corporate accounting; activate capital turnover; strengthen the effectiveness of social control over multinational corporations; it will allow optimal allocation of global resources.

Key words: corporate accounting, socio-economic, transaction costs, multinational corporations, equity, exchange capitalization, association, financial reporting, IFRS

Introduction

In recent years, there have been significant changes in the regulation of corporate accounting and reporting. This trend is primarily due to the strengthening of the role of accounting information in the management of the economic activities of the corporation. New requirements for corporate accounting and reporting are emerging due to the convergence of domestic accounting practices with internationally recognized ones.

Currently, many corporations have been created in our country, including with the participation of foreign capital. The process of internationalization of business presupposes the awareness of its participants at all stages of investing financial resources, their circulation and determining financial results. Corporate reporting, summarizing corporate accounting data, continues to be one of the most reliable sources of information.

The article "Current and modern problems of corporate accounting and reporting according to international standards" poses problematic issues of corporate accounting and reporting, an attempt to solve which is aimed at developing readers' skills of professional judgment on the studied aspects.

Literature review.

The steady growth of the gross domestic product, the improvement of the investment climate indicates the positive dynamics of the socio-economic development of the country, the strengthening of market relations, and the stabilization of the economy. To a large extent, this is the result of an increase in the efficiency of corporations, their business, financial and investment activity.

In the encyclopedic dictionary of F.A. Brockhaus, I.A. Efron, corporation is a common name for many types of unions that have an internal organization that unites the members of the union into a single whole, are the subject of rights and obligations, a legal entity [7].

In the modern dictionary of the Russian language, a corporation is 1) a united group, a circle of persons of the same profession, one class; 2) one of the forms of a monopolistic association [17].

In the economic and legal literature, at present, the definition of a corporation as an economic category is identified. "In joint-stock companies or corporations, they are the highest form of capital movement, the advantage of which is the adequacy of the corporate proper to the regulatory and market mechanisms of the economy of a mixed society" [2, p.115].

According to P. Stepanov, the term "corporation" comes from the Latin expression "corpus habere", reflecting the rights of a legal personality. Other authors note that the concept of "corporation" comes from the Latin "corporatio", which means association [32].

A number of authors consider a corporation as an association of several legal entities that does not have the status of a legal entity.

In our opinion, a modern large corporation in most cases appears as a set of legal entities jointly implementing common goals and interests.

The socio-economic basis of the corporation is corporate property, the main features of which are:

integrated property of economically independent entities that voluntarily pooled their individual capitals in order to ensure their sustainable reproduction on an innovative basis at the level of advanced achievements of scientific and technological progress;

corporate property that denies individual appropriation by the owner of the means of production, which is the associative property of diverse owners of capital, labor, entrepreneurship within the framework of a corporate association. The organizational and legal form of such an associative type of property is, as a rule, an open-type joint-stock company.

Financial and industrial groups are a certain form of integration, combining industrial, financial, commercial and banking capital under the responsibility of their central leading company. The main company of the financial and industrial group forms various companies and firms that are full participants in the share capital, and manages a multifaceted cycle - from production, management, financial support to control and sale of products in the domestic and foreign markets. The creation, formation of policies and strategies of financial and industrial groups is influenced by the legislative system of the state.

The internationalization of production and the development of productive forces have contributed to the emergence of transnational corporations (TNCs) - enterprises that own or control complexes of industries or service sectors located outside the country in which these corporations are based.

As for corporate accounting, it is inextricably linked with transactions through which economic values are transferred from one person to another. It is noted that it is business transactions that make up the essence of markets and are the basis of the company's activities. When concluding an agreement on the exchange of products, goods, services, transaction costs inevitably arise. The firm reaches its limit when the costs of additional operations within the firm become greater than the costs of the same operations performed through the market¹ [12].

Table 1.

Stages of formation and development of corporate accounting and reporting

Chronology	Prerequisites for development	The main directions of development
1	2	3
XV - XVIII c.c. Creation of corporations in European countries.	Creation of joint-stock companies on the basis of financing expeditions to discover new lands	Accounting objects and reporting elements: share capital, shares, settlements with shareholders. The main directions of development: the emergence of the era of the investor - the main user of corporate reporting. The appearance of fictitious joint-stock companies contributed to their ban for more than a hundred years.
XIX c.	Industrial revolutions, the need for large capital investments, the development of banks, the creation of exchanges, technical improvements, the expansion of trade.	Accounting objects and reporting elements: equity, financial instruments, transformation and transaction costs.
XX c.	Active construction of railways, formation of monopolies, development of communications, internationalization of production and capital, diversification, inflationary processes.	The main directions of development: separation of the functions of shareholders and managers, mandatory reporting to users, the need for audits, the formation of professional organizations of accountants

¹ Коуз Р. Г. Фирма, рынок, право / Р. Г. Коуз; Пер. с англ. – М.: «Дело ЛТД», 1993.

XXI c.	The information revolution is the globalization of business and the formation of the information economy.	and auditors.
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Main part

Transaction costs consist of costs that can be measured and costs that are difficult to measure, time to acquire information, standing in queues, paying bribes, etc., as well as losses from insufficient supervision and control. The presence of these immeasurable costs makes it difficult to accurately estimate the total transaction costs generated by a certain institution.

The main areas of the corporation's strategy inevitably cause transaction costs, the minimization of which will allow to win a certain market share. Transaction costs as an integral element of the corporation's economic activity provide access to property rights, resources, negotiating and concluding contracts, searching for information, evaluating and controlling the quality of resources, protecting resources and property rights, etc. The scale of costs is variable and is influenced by economic, political and legal factors.

The development of market relations has led to the emergence of various users of information, whose needs are presented in Table 2.

Table 2.

Информационные потребности пользователей бухгалтерских данных.

Type of information	External users		Internal users
	with a direct financial interest	with an indirect financial interest	
Assets	+	+	+
Income	+	+	+
Financial results	+	+	+
Taxable	-	+	-
Profit	+	-	+
Dividends paid	+	-	-
Return on investment	-	-	+
Efficiency of resources used	+	-	+
Ability to repay	-	-	+
loans received	+	-	+

Capital investment volumes	+	-	+
Sufficiency of funds	-	+	+
Ability to pay for deliveries on time	+	-	-
Change in equity share	-	-	+
Ability to pay interest on a loan	+	-	+
Stability and profitability of the organization	-	-	+
Amount and rate of return	-	-	+

When forming a system of corporate accounting and reporting, each country relies to some extent on legislative acts. The influence of professional organizations on the creation of a corporate accounting system varies. The documents of the legislative bodies include the "Law on the Activities of Companies" (Great Britain), the "Law on Accounting and Reporting" (Sweden), and in those countries where tax legislation is put in the first place – the "Law on Taxes" (Germany). In the USA, its own regulatory documents are used for various categories of reporting entities. In a number of countries, corporate accounting and reporting standards are developed by government organizations specially created for this purpose. For example, in Spain, the regulation of corporate accounting is under the jurisdiction of the Ministry of Economy and Finance, which has created an Institute of Accountants and Auditors to coordinate activities² [7]. The activities of commercial organizations in the country are regulated by the norms of the Commercial Code and the law on the activities of companies. This legislation establishes accounting principles, rules for the preparation of corporate reports and audits, as well as the publication of corporate reports. The main accounting procedures are described in detail in the general accounting plan, which includes the main and additional parts, where the principles, methods of evaluation, rules of accounting documentation are presented. The Institute of Accountants and Auditors periodically publishes a Bulletin containing comments, as well as amendments to the current legislation on accounting.

In some countries, regulatory documents may be issued by professional accounting organizations, for example, financial accounting Standards in the USA (FAS) and Financial

² Бухгалтерский учет в зарубежных странах: учеб. / отв. ред. Ф.Ф. Буты-нец. – М.: ТК Велби, Изд-во Проспект, 2005. М.: ИНФРА-М, 2000.

Reporting Standards (FRS) in the UK. In other countries, such as Canada, the law may require companies to comply with corporate accounting and reporting standards. In France, professional organizations also influence the setting of standards mainly by providing advice to legislative bodies. In Switzerland, professional organizations issue recommendations on corporate accounting, which are not mandatory, but provide significant assistance in the organization of corporate accounting. In Germany, professional organizations monitor compliance of accounting practices with the current legislation to a greater extent than they develop accounting procedures. Professional organizations try to gain recognition from users of their developments, which is possible only with a high level of their quality or the presence of a monopoly on the appointment of auditors who can indicate in audit reports that the audited organization does not meet the established requirements.

In the study of national models of corporate accounting regulation, scientists have identified factors that have a significant impact on the development of corporate accounting. The role of the state as a power-controlling system operating in each country was noted. The presence of competition drives market forces that regulate corporate accounting practices in accordance with market needs. Finally, the public opinion of practicing accountants also influences the formation of a corporate accounting system.

D. Blake and O. Amat distinguish four strategies for regulating corporate accounting: legalism, associativism and corporatism.

Under liberalism, regulation is carried out exclusively by the action of market principles. As an example, Sweden can be cited, where the professional organization of auditors has a great influence on the activities of specialists. For professional accountants, membership in this company is not mandatory, but most of them aspire to become a member. The professional organization of auditors publishes recommendations on accounting and auditing issues and publishes a large number of reference literature, including in English. The development of accounting theory and practice in Sweden is also influenced by scientific institutions. The influence of Germany and the USA is the strongest. This is due to the fact that the first accounting professors at the Stockholm and Gothenburg schools were Germans, as well as followers of E. Schmalenbach and F. Schmidt. The publication by a professional organization of auditors of a significant amount of American literature contributes to the strengthening of the influence of American theorists.

The legal framework of corporate accounting in Sweden provides

"The Law on the Activities of Companies" and "The Law on Accounting", according to which the Accounting Standards Council was established, which is under the control of the Ministry of Justice and includes representatives of the accounting profession, the tax service and a small number of full-time employees. The main task of the Council is to provide advisory services to the Government in the development of laws regulating corporate accounting.

Legalism presupposes the unconditional application of state principles. An example of legalism is Germany, which has a long and strong tradition of accounting. One of the main elements of German accounting legislation is the principle of obligation, that is, the provision of tax reports on the same basis as accounting documents. Accounting methods used to reflect commercial transactions are at the same time mandatory for calculating taxable profit. The Law on the Activities of Companies provides that accounting documents must be compiled in accordance with generally accepted accounting principles, and in practice most

decisions on accounting problems are based on the decisions of the Supreme Tax Court. A detailed and standardized accounting and reporting system was formed in the 30s, but even now, despite the presence of highly professional accounting specialists and the active activity of German scientists in this field, accounting standards and procedures are set by the government.

Currently, the integration of corporate accounting and reporting is carried out in two directions: harmonization and standardization.

One of the goals of the EU is to create a single sphere for entrepreneurial activity by harmonizing legislation on companies and taxation, as well as creating a common capital market. Each country may have a national accounting organization model and a system of standards regulating it that does not contradict similar standards in the EU member states.

Standardization of accounting procedures is implemented by the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB), established by the Foundation of the Committee on International Financial Reporting Standards. The Committee on International Financial Reporting Standards (IASB) was established on June 29, 1973 by representatives of professional public organizations of the following countries: Austria, Canada, Germany, France, Japan, Mexico, Holland, USA, Great Britain and Ireland.

In 2001, the IASB was reorganized into the International Accounting Standards Board (IASB), a non-governmental, professional organization funded by audit companies and associations of professional accountants and auditors. The IASB also receives funds from its developments. International standards issued before 2001 were called International Accounting Standards (IAS/IAS), and after 2001 - International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS/IFRS). To date, 25 IAS/IAS and 15 IFRS/IFRS have been developed.

In order to clarify certain provisions of the standards related to their practical application, the Standing Committee on Interpretations of Financial Statements (PKI/SIC) or the Committee on Interpretation of International Financial Statements (CIMFO/IFRIC) are developing interpretations - PKI/SIC (before 2001) and CIMFO/IFRIC (after 2001).

The essence the approach is to develop a unified set of standards containing principles and rules for the formation of financial statements applicable to use in any country.

Discussion & examples

The objectives of the IASB are:

- ✚ development, publication and promotion of IFRS, which must be followed in the preparation and presentation of financial statements;
- ✚ work to improve and harmonize rules, accounting standards and procedures related to the presentation of financial statements.

One of the activities of the IASB is convergence - the convergence of national standards of various countries with international standards. The convergence process involves joint activities of the IASB and national accounting regulatory authorities to develop IFRS.

In order to encourage financial activity and intensify efforts to accumulate capital, EU experts are dealing with the problems of harmonization of corporate accounting and are developing legal documents addressed to the participating countries - EU Directives.

The Directives define the basic rules of corporate accounting that are mandatory for all EU member states and act as a compromise between the EU member states, since they do not have the character of international law. The directives provide for the specifics of the

corporate accounting system of a particular country, and leave the freedom to choose the structure and form of corporate reports, as well as methodological development of standards.

A certain group of assets whose key characteristics are the inability to generate cash inflows independently of other assets or groups of assets (office buildings, electronic computing equipment, research center) are defined by IAS 36 as corporate assets. The value of such assets should be distributed among the generating units in proportion to the annual income from each generating unit. When testing a cash-generating unit for impairment, an entity is required to identify corporate assets related to a particular cash-generating unit.

Example 1.

The production division of the company, considered as a generating unit, has production equipment with a book value of 115.0 CU as of 31.12.18. The fair value of the equipment, taking into account selling expenses, is 98.2 cu. The cash flows generated by the division are presented in (Table 3.)

Table 3.

Cash flows of the generating unit

Years	Income	Expenses (without depreciation)
2018	80,0	30,0
2019	85,0	36,0
2020	50,0	40,0
2021	30,0	25,0
Total	245,0	131,0

Let's determine the value of use based on cash flows at a discount rate of 7%, taking into account all risks (Table 4.).

Table 4.

Calculation of the value of the use of the generating unit

Years	Net cash flow	Discount rate	Net discounted value = value in use
2018	50,0	0,9345	46,725
2019	49,0	0,8734	42,797
2020	10,0	0,8163	8,163
2021	5,0	0,7634	3,817
Total	-	-	101,502

The value in use exceeds the fair value fewer selling expenses, therefore, comparing it with the carrying amount at the date of the report, we determine the impairment loss of the generating unit in the amount of 13,498 CU (115,0 – 101,502). This amount will be included in the statement of financial results for 2019.

An impairment loss is recognized for a cash-generating unit if the recoverable amount is less than its carrying amount and is allocated first to business reputation and then to other assets in proportion to the carrying amount of each asset included in the cash-generating unit. When allocating an impairment loss, the carrying amount of the asset should not be lower than the largest value of the following values: net selling price; value in use; zero.

Example 2.

Upon acquisition of the company, goodwill amounted to 1,500 conventional units (cu) and was distributed into two generating units (divisions No. 1 and No. 2) in the ratio of 1,000 cu and 500 cu, Inventories are estimated at net sales price. At the end of the year, when testing generating unit No. 1 for impairment, its recoverable amount was 20,000 cu, and the carrying amount was 24,000 cu distribution coefficient = $(4000 - 1000) : (20\ 000 - 1000) = 0,158$. The distribution of the impairment loss is presented in Table 5.

Table
5.

Calculation of impairment loss

Indicators	Book value	Impairment	Recoverable amount
Goodwill	1000	(1000)	-
Fixed assets	13 000	(2052)	10948
Intangible assets	3 000	(474)	2526
Stocks	4 000	-	4000
Accounts receivable	3 000	(474)	2526
Total	24 000	(4000)	20 000

In subsequent reporting periods, the company must identify signs that contribute to reducing the impairment loss and determine the recoverable value of the asset. An impairment loss can be reduced if the following information is available:

- the market value of the asset increased significantly during the period;
- during the reporting period, there were significant positive changes in the company's working conditions (technological, market, economic, legal);
- during the reporting period, market interest rates or other market rates of return on investments decreased, which will affect the discount rate used in calculating the asset's value in use and will significantly increase the recoverable amount;
- internal reporting shows that the performance of the asset is higher, or will be higher than predicted.

In the presence of these signs and on the basis of the materiality principle, the impairment loss of the asset should be restored (reversed). The carrying amount of the asset increases to the recoverable amount, which, according to IAS 36, is the return of an impairment loss and is treated as a revaluation in accounting. The reversal of an impairment loss is recognized directly in the statement of financial results as profit. Upon recovery of an impairment loss on a revalued asset, the capital account is credited under the item "The amount of the revaluation".

The return of an impairment loss for a cash-generating unit and an increase in the value of its assets occurs by distributing it in proportion to the carrying amount of each asset included in the cash-generating unit, and then - business reputation. The loss from the impairment of business reputation in subsequent periods is not restored.

The financial statements should disclose information on groups of assets, individual assets, cash-generating units about each significant impairment loss recognized or reversed during the reporting period.

For each group of assets, the company is required to disclose:

- ✚ the amount of impairment losses recognized in the statement of financial results during the period and the items of the report reflecting the losses;
- ✚ the amount of refunds of impairment losses recognized in the statement of financial results during the period and the report items reflecting these amounts;
- ✚ the amount of impairment losses recognized in the equity account during the period;
- ✚ the amounts of the return of impairment losses recognized in the equity account during the period.

When recognizing an impairment loss or its recovery as significant, it is necessary to:

- ✚ to disclose the events or circumstances that caused;
- ✚ disclose the amount of the loss;
- ✚ characterize the asset or segment to which they belong.
- ✚ For an individual asset, it is necessary to disclose the nature of the asset and the reporting segment to which the asset belongs.

For the generating unit, it is necessary to disclose the name, the amount of the loss recognized or recovered.

Determining the fair value and selling costs, calculating discounted estimates of the estimated future cash flows expected from the use of an asset and its disposal, is a complex and expensive procedure.

The formation of corporate reporting by an organization with a deviation from the established rules leads to its intentional and unintentional distortions.

According to the degree of influence of errors on the reliability of corporate reporting, they are divided into significant and insignificant distortions. Distortions are considered insignificant if their omission (or non-detection) during the verification process does not change the indicators of corporate reporting in such a way that it will mislead users who use this information to make an appropriate decision. Types of distortions of corporate reporting are presented in Table 6.

Table 6.

Misrepresentations of corporate reporting

Classification feature	Виды искажений
By the degree of influence on reliability	Essential Non - essential
By the nature of occurrence	Unintentional: technical, arithmetic, typos, omissions of operations; Intentional: veiling of the balance sheet, contrary to legislation,

	tax violations, falsification of the balance sheet
By the object of encroachment	Cash; Material
In the circle of persons involved in the distortion of reporting	Management personnel; Employees; Investors
According to the method of reflecting the facts of economic life in accounting	Incompleteness of reflection of the facts of economic life; Unreasonableness of accounts; Errors in the periodization of facts of economic life; Errors in documenting the facts of economic life;
By the degree of influence on accounting information	Local Transit

Applying the materiality level indicator determined by calculation, it is necessary to take into account that some accounts may contain more errors than others. At the same time, possible distortions in the articles of corporate reporting may have a multidirectional character. For example, incorrect reflection of balances on cash and debtors accounts affects only these accounts and therefore is not common. However, a significant error in accounting for sales volumes is the most common type of inaccuracy. At the same time, it affects not only the volume of sales, but also the balance of accounts receivable, the amount of profit (loss) before taxation and net profit (loss) of the reporting period, the amount of tax payments. It seems to us the most expedient to establish the levels of materiality for significant elements of corporate reporting.

Conclusion

In the study of national models of corporate accounting regulation, scientists have identified factors that have a significant impact on the development of corporate accounting. The role of the state as a power-controlling system operating in each country was noted. The presence of competition drives market forces that regulate corporate accounting practices in accordance with market needs. Finally, the public opinion of practicing accountants also influences the formation of a corporate accounting system.

Summing up the results of the study of institutional support for the development of the accounting system, it should be noted the following. The legislation of each country participates in the regulation of the corporate accounting system. The role of professional accounting organizations in this process is also undeniable. The ratio of the degree of influence of state bodies and professional organizations differs significantly in different countries. In the USA, Great Britain, and the Netherlands, accounting specialists play a direct role in the formation of legislation, the development of accounting standards, and monitor their implementation. In France, professional organizations participate in the development of accounting standards and adopt non-binding corporate rules. In Switzerland, the recommendations of professional accounting organizations are widely used by practicing

accountants, although they are not mandatory. In Germany, professional organizations mainly monitor the compliance of accounting practices with current legislation, as well as advise legislative bodies in the development of new methods and procedures for corporate accounting.

Thus, the integration of the development of corporate accounting and reporting gives positive results in the improvement of regulatory legal acts regulating the requirements of publicity: the volume of disclosed information is increasing, the conditions for disclosure of financial statements are becoming more and more formalized.

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